

Exchange Behaviour of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ in Amberlite IRC-50

J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI

Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University, Dist. Darjeeling

Manuscript received 12 March 1971; revised 28 February 1973; accepted 23 April 1973

Cation exchange studies of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ have been carried out from Na-Coen₃-Amberlite IRC-50 resin against different ions. The order of release of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ from the resin matrix is in the sequence: Cs < Rb < K < Na < Li < NH₄ < Mg < Ca. The quaternary ammonium ions, such as (CH₃)₄N, (C₂H₅)₄N, CTA (cetyltri-methylammonium) and CP (cetyl pyridinium) fail completely to exchange $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ from its resin complex. The plots of log (selectivity co-efficient) vs. hydrated ionic radii as well as reciprocal of the Debye Huckel parameter a° give linear graphs suggesting that both the parameters may be found to correlate with the relative affinities of the ions for the resin surface.

IN recent years ion exchange studies of resins with common cations have been extensively carried out by different workers¹⁻⁸ on various aspects but such studies with inorganic trivalent complex cations⁹ are rather meagre. The physico chemical aspects of many of these reactions being still unknown in their fundamental details, constitute one of the objectives of the present investigation. It is in this context that an attempt has been made to study the ion exchange characteristics of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ on Amberlite IRC-50.

Experimental

Amberlite IRC-50 (Rohm and Haas Co.), a carboxylic acid type exchanger, (16-50 mesh) was converted into its H-form by passing 1.0 M HCl solution repeatedly through a column of the resin. The exchange capacity of the H-resin was found to be 1025 me per 100 g of the oven dry resin at 105° by back titration of excess NaOH with HCl in presence of 5% NaCl solution. To prepare Na-Coen₃-resin the Na-resin prepared in the usual manner¹⁰ was mixed with Coen₃Cl₃ in concentrations approximately 3000 me/100 g i.e., about three times the exchange capacity. After 24 hr the excess salt was washed out with distilled water and the Na-Coen₃-resin thus formed was dried in vacuum and its moisture content was 6.5 g/100 g of resin. For exchange studies the Na-Coen₃-resin was weighed accurately (~0.15 g) in pyrex bottles to which varying amounts of exchanging electrolytes were added. The volume was kept constant (10 ml) in each case by adding water. They were also shaken for two or three hours, kept overnight and Coen₃Cl₃ content of the solution was measured with Zeiss photoelectric grating colorimeter 'Spekol' at 470 nm.

The hydration characteristics of the resinsates (H⁺, Na⁺, Mg²⁺, $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$) were determined in the modified apparatus of Baver¹¹ after drying the appropriate forms in vacuum for 48 hr. A pyrex glass crucible with a sintered base is the main part of the apparatus. The bottom of the crucible is

specially designed and joined with a straight graduated tube of fine bore through standard joint. The vacuum dried resinate is taken and quickly placed on the base, the crucible being covered with a special lid of ground glass ending in a fine capillary. The flow of water through the graduated tube gives the index of the volume of water taken up by the resinate. The results are expressed in ml/g after blank correction for the same equilibrium period. Since all the measurements were done under identical conditions the intake of water per g of the resinate gives an idea about the relative hydration status of the solid.

Results and Discussion

The maximum exchange of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ on Na-resin corresponds to about 1000 me/100 g. The results of exchange of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ from Na-Coen₃-resin by inorganic ions are recorded in Table 1. It can be seen from the selectivity coefficient values that the general lyotrope series is reversed in the case of monovalent ions although the behaviour of NH₄⁺ is some what different. The divalent ions, however, exhibit the normal behaviour. It is clear from the following data that when the exchangeable hydrogen is replaced from the exchanger by sodium or magnesium the corresponding resinsates exhibit a hydrophilic character while, the hydrogen being replaced by $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ ion, the solid becomes hydrophobic.

Intake of water by resinsates

From	ml of water per gm of the resinate
Na	3.6
Mg ²⁺	3.3
H ⁺	2.1
Coen ₃ ⁺	1.8

Martin and Glaeser¹² have also noted the water-proof character developed in clay minerals when ions like $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$ are present in the exchangeable form. Owing to the presence of a hydrophobic layer, ions such as Li, Na, K etc. are not easily accessible to the

surface unless a considerable amount of the exchangeable $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ ions get exchanged and replaced by hydrophilic ones. At lower concentrations of the exchanging ions, therefore, the amount of exchange is very small. At higher concentrations of the electrolyte the hydrophobic ions are replaced by hydrophilic ones making the resin more accessible to water as well as to the exchanging ions with the result that ion exchange increases.

The order of preference in releasing the exchangeable $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ ions appears to be $\text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$; the result is rather unusual. This may be explained on the basis of the polarizability and hydrophobic character of the complex ion which is present in the solid matrix, the presence of which facilitates the removal of water from the ingoing hydrated alkali metal ions, Li, Na, K etc. The sizes of the unhydrated ions play predominant role in the ion exchange process. Similar results for weak acid carboxylate and phosphate resins have been obtained by Gregor *et al.*⁵, Bregman¹³, Lindenbaum and Boyd¹⁴, Becker, Lindenbaum and Boyd⁸ and also for hydrous Zirconia by Britz and Nancollas¹⁵. The higher exchanging power of NH_4^+ is probably due to low pH of NH_4Cl solution at higher concentrations studied where H^+ is present in appreciable amounts.

The selectivity coefficients (Table I) have been calculated as in our previous paper¹⁶ assuming the exchange equilibrium as

where the bar refers in the resin phase and Z is the valency of the exchanging ions. The values of their mean activity coefficients in solution are taken from literature^{17,18}.

In order to ascertain the role of hydration^{19,20} of ions some experiments have also been carried out in 50% aqueous-ethanolic medium with Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ . It is observed that in each case the amount of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ released is larger than in the aqueous medium and the order of preference is: $\text{K}^+ < \text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+$. This sequence which is a deviation from the lyotrope series, may be explained on the basis of solvation of these ions, the resulting ionic sizes, their activities and the dielectric properties of the solvent mixture.

Attempts to replace $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ from its resin complex by quaternary ammonium ions, such as $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}$, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}$ CTA and CP show that no release takes place within the concentration range studied for $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$ (0.5 *M*) and CTABr and CPCL (0.05 *M*). This may be due to a very strong affinity of $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ for the resin and the comparatively large dimension of the quaternary ammonium ions. This interesting observation indicates that Na-Coen₃-IRC-50 may be used for the separation of the relatively small inorganic ions from a mixture containing large organic ions.

It may be noted that the plot of the hydrated ionic radius²¹ as well as the reciprocal of the Debye Huckel parameter $a^{\circ 22}$ against \log (selectivity coefficient) is, unlike that observed with clay minerals²³⁻²⁵ linear. This shows that both the hydrated ionic radius and the Debye Huckel parameter a° may be utilized to correlate the affinities of the ions for the resin. The plot of \log (selectivity coefficient) vs. $1/a^{\circ}$ is, however, on the basis of the simple model of Pauley²⁶ which suggests that electrostatic attraction between the counter ions and fixed ionic groups is the significant factor.

References

- O. D. BONNER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 719.
- O. D. BONNER and F. L. LIVINGSTON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 530.
- G. E. MYERS and G. W. BOYD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 521.
- C. E. MARSHALL and G. GARCIA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 1663.
- H. P. GREGOR, M. J. HAMILTON, R. J. OZA and F. BERNSTEIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 263.
- H. P. GREGOR, M. J. HAMILTON, J. BECKER and F. BERNSTEIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 874.
- L. POCHHALI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 521.
- K. E. BECKER, S. LINDENBAUM and G. E. BOYD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 3834.
- T. MATSUURA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, 27, 2269.
- R. KUNIN, "Ion Exchange Resins", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., N.Y., 1958.

TABLE I. EXCHANGE CHARACTERISTICS OF $[\text{Coen}_3]^{3+}$ WITH RESPECT TO DIFFERENT IONS FROM Na-Coen₃-IR-50

Electrolyte used	Concentration of electrolyte	Selectivity Coefficient
1 : 1 electrolyte		
LiCl	3.0×10^{-1} (M)	0.0965
	5.0 "	0.196
	7.0 "	0.282
NaCl	3.0×10^{-1} (M)	0.0687
	5.0 "	0.126
	7.0 "	0.205
	8.0 "	0.258
KCl	3.0×10^{-1} (M)	0.0298
	5.0 "	0.0584
	7.0 "	0.124
	8.0 "	0.140
NH ₄ Cl	3.0×10^{-1} (M)	0.198
	5.0 "	0.353
	7.0 "	0.492
RbCl	3.0×10^{-1} (M)	0.0209
	4.0 "	0.0360
	5.0 "	0.0520
CsCl	3.0×10^{-1} (M)	0.0177
	3.5 "	0.0213
	4.0 "	0.0298
2 : 1 electrolyte		
MgCl ₂	4.0×10^{-2} (M)	0.463
	7.0 "	0.527
	10.0 "	0.557
CaCl ₂	4.0×10^{-2} (M)	0.621
	7.0 "	0.717
	10.0 "	0.736

11. L. D. BAYER, "Soil Physics", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., N.Y., 1946.
12. I. MARTIN and R. GLAESER, *Bull. Groupe Franc. Argiles*, 1960, **12**, 83.
13. J. I. BREGMAN, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, **57**, 125.
14. S. LINDENBAUM and G. E. BOYD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 2374.
15. D. BRITZ and G. H. NANCOLLAS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3861.
16. J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Colloid and Interface Sci.*, 1971, **35**, 295.
17. C. E. MARSHALL and L. O. EIME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1302.
18. B. E. CONWAY, "Electrochemical Data", 1952, p. 62, 63, 76-78, Elsevier Publishing Co.
19. A. CHATTERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **7**, 37.
20. A. CHATTERJEE and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 674.
21. LANDOLT-BÖRNSTEINS TABELLEN, ERGÄNZUNGSBAND, 1936, **97C**, 2059.
22. R. H. STOKES and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1870.
23. J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 281.
24. J. L. DAS KANUNGO, S. K. CHAKRAVARTI and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 685.
25. J. L. DAS KANUNGO and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI, *Kolloid Z. und Z. Polymere*, 1971, **248**, 953.
26. J. L. PAULEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1422.